

PLAN OVERVIEW

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: *Sustainable photocatalytic nanostructures for environmental applications assisted by magnetic fields: water remediation and air quality monitoring (WARM)*

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Project abstract:

Environmental and energy issues represent topics of growing interest and social concern due to rapid demographic growth and strong economic development. In particular, a worrying problem is the growing pollution of water and air, which gives rise to different health problems (cancer, ischemic heart disease, obstructive pulmonary disease...) and threatens biodiversity, contributing to the mass extinction of species. Finding technological solutions to reduce pollution, leading to cleaner air and water, with lower energy costs, should be a social commitment for current and future generations. In this sense, the WARM project focuses, firstly, on the development of new materials to be used in photocatalytic processes in order to eliminate contaminants in water and, secondly, on the design of new sensors to monitor air pollution. In both cases, the common strategy to improve their performance in terms of effectiveness, efficiency and cost reduction is based on magnetic technology.

The data management plan (DMP) of the project is being developed taking into account the Open Science practices. The DMP is a living document, which will be updated as required.

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Sustainable Photocatalytic Nanostructures For Environmental Applications Assisted By Magnetic Fields: Water Remediation And Air Quality Monitoring (Warm)

DATA SUMMARY

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?

No previous data has been reused.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

The project will produce mainly experimental procedures and data results that will be properly defined employing open science formats. Concretely files with the following extensions are mainly expected: Text: TXT (automatized laboratory experiments with LabVIEW, UV-Vis Spectroscopy, Vibrating Sample Magnetometry, VSM); Tabular data: CSV or DAT from SQUID measurements and TGA/DSC; Documents: RTF or PDF; Images: PNG (SEM and TEM micrographs); Compressed data: ZIP; binary hierarchical data: HDF5, .raw and .brml for XRD diffractograms)

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The purpose of the data generation and re-use is to develop, characterize, and optimize novel magnetic-based materials and devices for water remediation and air quality monitoring. The data will be used to design and test photocatalytic materials capable of removing water contaminants, as well as to develop and validate gas sensors boosted by magnetic technology for detecting air pollutants. All datasets, models, and protocols will support the evaluation of performance, reproducibility, and scalability of the developed systems, and will be shared for further research and innovation in environmental technologies. These data are fundamental for the project tasks and objectives:

- Development of magnetic photocatalytic materials for water purification.
- Design and optimization of gas sensors boosted by magnetic technology for air pollution monitoring.
- Validation of experimental results.
- Dissemination and sharing of scientific results and datasets with the research community

To ensure traceability between objectives, tasks, and research outputs, datasets are organized and published according to the corresponding work packages, as summarized in the following table:

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

Generated data has an expected size up to 10 GB, including raw and processed experimental datasets, microscopy and spectroscopy images, sensor response measurements, and analytical reports. Re-used data (e.g., reference pollutant concentrations or material standards) will represent less than 5% of the total volume.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The generated data will originate from **experimental work** carried out in the project, including raw data, results, negative results, postprocessed data and experimental methods.

Structural, morphological, optical, electronic and magnetic characterization data. Different pieces of equipment were used: X-Ray Diffraction (BRUKER D8 ADVANCE ECO), TEM Microscopy (TECNAI T20), SEM Microscopy (THERMO SCIENTIFIC PHENOM PRO), BET (MICROMETRICS GEMINI V), TGA/DSC (METLER TOLEDO TGA/DSC 3+), VSM Magnetometry (LABMADE), SQUID Magnetometry (QUANTUM DESIGN MPMS XL), UV-Vis Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy (SHIMADZU 2600 UV-Vis).

The following equipment was employed for the photocatalytic experiments: T70 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (PG Instruments LTD), UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (UV-16 LABOLAN), Xenon Short Arc Lamp (SCIENCETECH).

The following equipment was employed for the gas sensor development: electronic signal conditioning equipment (namely, oscilloscopes, signal generators, lock-in amplifiers, multimeters) high resistance electrometer (Keithley 6517B), LaBVIEW 2014 for automatized measurements, UV and visible range LEDs and gas testing unit.

All of the previously mentioned analyses were performed at the Public University of Navarra, except TEM Microscopy and UV–Vis Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy, which were performed at SAI Universidad de Zaragoza and Instituto de Síntesis Química y Catálisis Homogénea (Zaragoza) respectively.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The data will be useful to researchers and engineers working in the fields of magnetic materials, photocatalysis, and environmental sensor development, as well as to industries and technology developers interested in sustainable water and air purification systems.

FAIR DATA

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Considering the Open Science practices, scientific data will be made FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable).

To make data findable, it will be shared in one or many records or uploads (datasets), each dataset will be provided with a persistent DOI (digital object identifier). Zenodo will be used as the repository to host the datasets and assign the corresponding DOI, ensuring long-term accessibility and traceability.

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Datasets will be provided with the metadata required by the employed repository. In any case, data will be described by normalized metadata standards and vocabularies (e.g. Zenodo uses JSON-schema for rich metadata and can export metadata to other standards such as Dublin Core. Zenodo also uses FAIR or open vocabularies including DataCite's Metadata Schema, Open Definition, FundRef, OpenAIRE).

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

In any case, keywords will be provided in the dataset metadata to enhance discovery (as long as the repository allows it, e.g. zenodo allows it).

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata: Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Repositories that make metadata collectable and indexable (searchable) will be chosen (e.g. Zenodo sends metadata to DataCite servers).

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

This information (whether temporary, permanent, open public, restricted or only available within the research team) will be properly posted making use of public repositories as Zenodo or Figshare. In any case, trusted repositories will be preferred.

UPNA institutional repository (academica-e, <https://academica-e.unavarra.es/>) will be employed to share preprints compatible with the particular editorial requirements as well as open access papers. In fact, this institutional

repository of UPNA uses national and international standards for the documents descriptors and complies with the interoperability protocol OAI-PMH (Open Access Initiative-Protocol for Metadata Harvesting). It is also collected by OPEN Aire (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe), meeting all its requirements and directives.

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Considered repositories are free to use, specifically, academia-e is the institutional repository managed by the University of the Principal Investigators.

2.2. Making data accessible - Repository: Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

The preferred Zenodo repository can assign an identifier or DOI to the data. Moreover, academia-e repository assigns a specific url (identifier).

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions.

Provided no restriction linked to their exploitation and intellectual property potential, all generated data will be reviewed and selected for publication in open-access repositories. The datasets supporting scientific publications will be made openly available through repositories such as Zenodo (or equivalent), following the FAIR principles. In cases where data cannot be openly shared — for instance, due to confidentiality agreements, potential industrial applications, or ongoing patent procedures — access will be temporarily restricted until protection measures are completed. All scientific papers resulting from the project will be published in Open Access.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

If an embargo is applied, it will be used only to allow sufficient time for the publication of research findings or for the protection of intellectual property, such as patent applications. The embargo period will be kept to the minimum necessary and will not normally exceed 3 months, unless justified by ongoing protection or publication processes. After the embargo period, all data will be made openly available in accordance with FAIR principles and Horizon Europe guidelines.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Data made open will be free and easy to access in their repository. Access to restricted data can be freely asked to the dataset owner (the researcher who uploads the record to the repository) by email or by the messaging tools provided by each repository.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

Data requests will be handled on a case by case basis by the dataset owner using email or the messaging tools provided by each repository.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

If the identity of the person accessing the data is relevant, an institutional email address will be required. Since the project does not manage sensitive data, the identity of the persons accessing the data is not recorded.

2.2. Making data accessible - Data:

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

There is no need for a data access committee, as there is no personal or sensitive data involved.

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Metadata will be made openly available based on the repository policy, e.g. zenodo licenses metadata under a public domain dedication (CC0). The metadata will include all necessary information to enable users to access the data, ensuring transparency and facilitating data reuse. If there are any exceptions to this approach, they will be justified with clear reasons, such as confidentiality, security, or legal constraints.

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Data will remain available and findable as long as the repositories exist, which is expected to be a long term given the choice of trusted repositories. Metadata can remain available if the data is not, as this information is harvested by search engines, or sent to metadata databases (depends on the repository, zenodo sends the metadata to DataCite servers).

2.2. Making data accessible - Metadata:

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Documentation required to access or read the data will be included in the datasets, or linked between datasets, as a general rule datasets and folders will contain at least a readme.txt file explaining the data and how to read it and which software (if any) is required. Software will not be included in the datasets.

2.3. Making data interoperable:

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

To ensure data interoperability and facilitate reuse across disciplines, the project will adopt standardized and widely used open data formats (e.g. CSV for tabular data, TXT for raw instrument outputs, PNG for microscopy images, HDF5 for hierarchical or large datasets).

All tabular datasets will include standardized headers with explicit variable names, units expressed in the International System of Units (SI), and clear descriptions of experimental conditions.

When project-specific terminology or experimental parameters are used, they will be clearly defined in accompanying documentation and mapped, where possible, to commonly used concepts in the fields of photocatalysis, magnetic materials and gas sensing.

To make data interoperable, standardized open formats will be preferred (see previous question about data formats).

2.3. Making data interoperable:

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

The project uses common terms; however, in case of using uncommon ontologies or vocabularies these will be explained in the dataset readme or the published method or appendix.

2.3. Making data interoperable:

Will your data include qualified references[1] to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

[1]A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Datasets will contain qualified references to other datasets or publications of the project as needed (particularly, methodologies used to obtain a dataset may be explained in detail in a publication, while a dataset may be linked to a particular publication).

2.4. Increase data re-use:

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

As a general rule datasets and folders will contain at least a readme.txt file with information required to re-use the data files (variable definitions, units of measurement, methodologies, software required), extensive methodologies may be explained in an open access publication which will be linked to the pertinent dataset.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Datasets and publications will be licensed under standard reuse licenses, a Creative Common CC BY license will be preferably selected.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Since the data produced in the project (except any with legal or size restrictions) will be eventually made open in a repository under a reuse license, the datasets will be useable by third parties, partially during the project and especially some time after the end of the project.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The provenance of the data will be documented in the readme files and translated to standard metadata when the repository supports it (when applicable, information about other source datasets, origin organization and place of the data, issue date, kind of data creation/collection method).

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Whenever possible, the peer review process will be the main pillar of data quality assurance. The review process for scientific data publication will be used to ensure the quality of the generated data. In addition, review and feedback

tools in data repositories will further enhance the peer review process. If this is not possible, the data will be reviewed by the investigators involved in the project.

2.4. Increase data re-use:

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

Since personal/sensitive data or consent form are not necessary in the project, no special data security or ethics are required.

OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Physical outputs will include synthesized magnetic photocatalytic materials, sensor prototypes, and reference samples used for testing water and air pollutants. Their preparation and storage will follow standardized laboratory procedures to ensure traceability, safety, and potential future reuse. Ownership, preservation, and sharing of these materials will comply with institutional policies and any applicable intellectual property or safety regulations.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Physical prototypes and material samples are not data so FAIR principles are not applicable.

Physical research outputs cannot be shared in the same way, and will be stored in the University Department for a few years, the Principal Investigators will consider any access or reuse request of physical items in a case by case basis.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

The costs associated with making data and other research outputs FAIR are expected to be negligible or not precisely quantifiable. Digital datasets will be stored and shared through open-access repositories (e.g. Zenodo), which do not involve additional costs. Physical outputs, such as prototypes and material samples, are not bulky and will be managed within the standard laboratory resources. Toxic or hazardous gases analyzed during the project will not be stored after the project's completion, avoiding additional storage or disposal costs.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

In the case of the costs of making research outputs FAIR exists, they will be handled by the University and/or the repository sponsors.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

The PI Juan Jesús Beato López will be responsible for data management plan (as stated in the project's work plan, task 5.4). Alternative: Cristina Gómez Polo.

Metadata generation (includes uploading/owning the datasets/records in repositories), data generation/collection/analysis can be performed by any member of the team.

External data centers are responsibility of their respective owners: CERN's zenodo, Universidad de Navarra's academica-e, Elsevier journals, AIP Publishing journals.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Data will be preserved as long as the repositories exist, which is expected to be a long term given the choice of trusted repositories. Cost is negligible. Principal Investigators decide what data is kept (see FAIR principles above).

DATA SECURITY

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

During the course of research activities, the data is stored on researchers' laptops and computer hard drives, and backed up frequently to both external storage and cloud storage (the University provides Microsoft's One Drive cloud storage for free to its researchers). Each researcher is responsible for their generated data at this point and must submit the data to the Principal Investigators when asked. The data will be uploaded to long term storage (repositories) as previously detailed. Since personal or sensitive data is not expected, no special data security is required.

ETHICS

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

There are no ethics or legal issues impacting data sharing, at the moment.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No personal data (or consent questionnaires) are required.

OTHER ISSUES

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Data management takes in mind Open Science practices (e.g. FAIR data, open access), as required by the funder.

PLANNED RESEARCH OUTPUTS

Title	DOI	Type	Release date	Access level	Repository (ies)	File size	License	Metadata standard	May contain sensitive data?	May contain PII?
WARM Management (DMP) Data Plan	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18982595	DMP	12/03/2026	Open	Zenodo	-	CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No
Dual approach for effective photodegradation and mineralization of carbamazepine using a ternary ZnFe ₂ O ₄ /(P,S)-g-C ₃ N ₄ /Two-Dimensional TiO ₂ composite	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsomega.5c08594	Journal Article	January 28, 2026	Open	None specified		CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No
Comparison of ibuprofen photodegradation by persulfate-assisted and magnetic field-assisted photocatalysis processes	https://academic.elsevier.com/abstract/S0169-2706(24)004405-b88d-e71f321a8867	Journal Article	May 2026	Open and accessible from April 2028	UPNA repository Academia-e		Copyright is held by Elsevier	None specified	No	No
Magnetic Fe-C nanocomposites via the thermal decomposition of fructose: efficient phenol adsorption	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2026.132640	Journal Article		Open	None specified		Creative Commons	None specified	No	No
Experimental setup program control	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19707728	Software	23 April 2026	Open	Zenodo		None specified	None specified	No	No
Photocatalytic structures Gas Sensor Fabrication WARM 2026	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19709529		23 April 2026	Open	Zenodo		CC-BY-4.0	None specified	No	No